

A STUDY ON THE SIGNIFICANCE OF POSITIVE PARENTING FOR GENERATION ALPHA

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to determine the importance of positive parenting for the alpha generation. Positive parenting has a great impact on a child's development. Generation Alpha is different from other generations of children. Handling them is very dangerous and parents need proper guidance. Positive parenting is about showing love, warmth and kindness to children and helping them grow up better. The results of this study show that a positive parenting approach is extremely important when dealing with the alpha generation. The influence of discipline is reflected in a child's growth. Research Design: The researcher followed a descriptive research design for the study. World of research: The world of this research comes from "parents of the alpha generation." Sample: The researcher took her sample of 60 respondents from a group of alpha generation parents. Sampling method: Convenient sampling method.

KEYWORDS: Positive parenting, Generation Alpha, Handling, Children.

INTRODUCTION:

Positive parenting is all about a positive relationship between parent and child. Positive parenting shows love, warmth, and kindness. It is about guiding children to do what they want through encouragement and encouragement. Becoming a parent is a big responsibility. It is about leading, directing, teaching, caring, empowering, nurturing, being sensitive to the child's needs, and being consistently and always nonviolent. Parents also ensure regular open communication, affection, emotional safety, emotional warmth, and unconditional love, recognize the good, respect the child's developmental level, and reward success. , you need to set boundaries, support your child's well-being, and show empathy for their feelings. Positive parenting is a powerful approach. The idea is to focus on your child's strengths rather than trying to correct their weaknesses. That's why some people call this strength-based parenting. Family and youth violence is increasingly recognized as an important public health problem in developing countries. Parenting interventions are important evidence-based strategies to prevent violence against and by children, but the most rigorous trials of parenting interventions have been conducted in high-income countries and far less in low- and middle-income countries.

DEFINITION:

Positive parenting:

Positive parenting means showing love, warmth, and kindness to your children. It is about guiding children to behave in the way they want through encouragement and guidance. It's about helping children grow by sending them a powerful message: You're loved, you're good, and you matter.

Generation Alpha:

Generation Alpha is the demographic cohort that follows Generation Z. Researchers and popular media use the early 2010s as the first birth year and the mid-to-late 2020s as the last birth year.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Nasir & Iqbal (2015) in this study focused on the proven influence of demographic variables in predicting emotional intelligence, representing the most constructive factors for the development of emotional competence. The essential reason for emotional helplessness

and inability to interact with others was the poverty of the parents. It has been proven that uncontrollable events affect children's emotions and that a better environment leads to better outcomes. . Even when a child reacts negatively to a situation, it may be due to social changes or changes in the family environment.

Carmeli & Josman, (2006) this study shows that it is important to take emotional intelligence into account. Many studies have already shown that there is a close relationship between parental SES and adolescent behavior and emotional intelligence of the wards, so in this article we will discuss how alpha generation attempts to examine the emotional issues faced by alpha generation.

Holroyd (2011) concludes in this study that despite close interaction with online learning, the alpha generation takes longer to learn and grows faster due to the influence of technology. Researchers noted that this generation is surrounded by material concepts and has strong problem-solving skills. Researchers have shown characteristics of the alpha generation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Parents can actively listen and respond sensitively to their children's concerns. This allows Gen Alphas to feel heard and understood which in turn promotes social and emotional development. Encourage children to recognize differences in their experiences. It also helps parents empathize with their children. Generation Alpha is characterized by the fact that they are digital natives and spend hours sitting in front of a screen. The technological advances that humanity has experienced in the 21st century are transforming the planet and its inhabitants both socially and economically.

Methodology of the Study

Objective of the Study

- To study the personal profile of the respondents.
- To access the level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the respondents.
- To discover the association between personal profile and significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the respondents.

- To analyze the difference between personal profile and significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the respondents.
- To study the influence of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the respondents.

Research design: The researcher followed descriptive research design for the study.

Universe of the study: Universe of the study: The universe of the present study is from, Parents of Generation Alpha.

Sampling: Sampling: The researcher took the sampling of 60 respondents from Parents of Generation Alpha. Sampling method: Purposive sampling method.

Tools for data collection: Researcher had used Mandleco, Barbara Olsen, Susanne Frost Hart, Craig H. The significance positive parenting and generation Alpha Questionnaire (PSDQ; Robinson et al., 1995) is a 32-item self-report measure that assesses significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.

The statistical tools applied by the researcher are Percentage Analysis, Chi-square, T-test and ANOVA.

Finds of the Study

PERSONAL PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Factors	MEDIUM	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age	31yrs-40yrs	35	58%
Gender	Female	38	63%
Marital Status	Married	60	100%
No. of Dependents	2-4	39	65%
Locality	Semi urban	37	62%
Educational Qualification	UG	34	57%
Occupation	Self employment	40	67%
Monthly Income (in Rs.)	Below –Rs.15000	37	62%
Type of organization	Private	20	33%

- ✓ Nearly (58%) of the respondents is in the age group between 31-40 years.
- ✓ More than half (63%) of the respondents are female.
- ✓ All most (100%) of the respondents are married.
- ✓ Majority (65%) of the respondents are number of dependents of 2-4.
- ✓ Nearly (62%) of the respondents are locality of semi urban.
- ✓ More than half (57%) of the respondents are UG level of educational qualification.
- ✓ Nearly (67%) of the respondents are occupation of self employed.
- ✓ Majority (62%) of the respondents are monthly income of below-Rs15000.
- ✓ Nearly (33%) of the respondents are working private type organization.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the Respondents

Level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	Frequency	Percentage %
Good	22	37
Moderate	14	23
Poor	24	40
Total	60	100.0

The table reveals that majority (37%) of the respondent's level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha was moderate. 40 percent of the respondents are with poor level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha. 23 percent of the respondents are with good level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.

Influence of personal profile and significance positive parenting and generation Alpha of the respondents

Variables	Statistical tool	Value	Result
Education and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	t-test	t= 1.895 P<0.05	Significant
Marital status and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	t-test	t= 3.725 P>0.05	Not Significant
Locality and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	t-test	t= 1.095 P<0.05	Significant
Age and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	ANOVA	F= .091 P>0.05	Not Significant
Type of organization and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	ANOVA	F = 5.691 P<0.05	Significant
Experience and level of significance	ANOVA	F= .107	Not-Significant

positive parenting and generation Alpha		P>0.05	
Income and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha	ANOVA	F = 5.091 P<0.05	Significant

Findings

- ❖ There is significant difference in the education and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is no significant marital status and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is significant difference in the locality and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is no significant difference in the age and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is significant difference in the type of organization and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is no significant difference in the experience and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.
- ❖ There is significant difference in the Income and level of significance positive parenting and generation Alpha.

SUGGESTIONS

1. Parents should encourage their children to express their thoughts and feelings openly and to actively listen.
2. Respondents should be conscious of promoting independence and self-reliance.
3. Emphasis on technology education.
4. Provide opportunities for cultural awareness and social experience.
5. Parents can actively listen and respond sensitively to their child's concerns.
6. This allows Generation Alpha to feel heard and understood which promotes social and emotional development.
7. Generation Alpha can maintain the status quo and move forward with confidence.

CONCLUSION

Generation Alpha was born into a fully technologically advanced and connected world, so they are adept at using digital devices and platforms. Through technology, we have seamless access to a wide range of information and entertainment resources. This generation is more independent and self-determined than previous generations. Almost 9 out of 10 Gen Alpha parents (89%) feel a unique sense of tension in their role. It's a desire to support children's success while recognizing the importance of giving them space to fail and outrageous experiences from which to learn. The survey concluded that 37% of respondents placed moderate importance on positive parenting and alpha generation. 40% of those surveyed place little importance on positive parenting or alpha generation. 23% of those surveyed have a positive meaning for positive parenting and the alpha generation.

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